

Evaluating user experience with the DARE platform

Report on the second usability evaluation of the DARE platform (Nov-Dec 2020)

Authors: Valentina Andries and Aurora Constantin¹
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ABSTRACT

This document presents the findings of the second usability evaluation of the DARE platform, which was a pilot qualitative study with six participants. The study consisted of semi-structured interviews conducted online, with participants with computing skills and with varying levels of involvement in the development of the DARE platform. The results of this small-scale evaluation showed that the DARE platform is perceived to be usable, relatively easy to use (depending on the user's background) and versatile. However, training needs were also highlighted, as well as a number of suggestions for improvement.

¹ School of Informatics, University of Edinburgh

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1 DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDY

1.1 Aims

The interview-study aims were to evaluate:

1. The ease of use of the DARE platform
2. The perceived user satisfaction with the platform
3. The impact of the platform on researchers' productivity and innovation in research communities
4. Potential usability and functionality issues, as identified or anticipated by the participants
5. Suggestions to improve the platform

1.2 Participants

We have recruited 6 participants, from various backgrounds. Two of them helped us to pilot the interview questions. All of them have been involved in the development of the platform to varying extents, and they all have programming skills. More specifically, computational skills are expected for the participants' roles, namely those of research engineers in two cases, as well as for the other participants who had contributed to the DARE platform by developing the DARE API (backend) for example, or by co-developing with domain experts one of the workflows to be included in the platform.

1.3 Methods

We conducted semi-structured interviews to obtain insights arising from participants' perspectives and experiences. The interview questions were developed to probe several areas of exploration, such as the ease of use of the DARE platform, its learnability, its potential for integration with other services, and for automation of research methods. Questions about data-use policies were also included.

Initially, we piloted the interviews with two DARE team members. This tested our interview questions and interview data-collection procedure.

1.4 Procedure

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the School of Informatics (University of Edinburgh), where the researchers who conducted this study work. Electronic consent was obtained from the participants by means of emails as the data collection took place during the pandemic, and social distancing rules had to be observed. Some of the participants were provided with the interview questions prior to the interview session, as per their request. The semi-structured script can be found in Appendix A.

2 DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

The data has been collected online, using the Zoom platform for video-conferencing. The sessions were recorded for analysis purposes. Similar to the first usability evaluation, which involved international BSc and MSc students from KIT (Karlsruhe Institute of Technology) Geophysics programmes, a thematic analysis top-down approach was employed [1]. Codes were given to the participants (from P1 to P6) to maintain anonymity in reports and publications. Some pre-defined themes of interest had already been defined, and they were reflected in the interview questions, however other themes could also emerge.

The analysis started with a set of pre-defined themes, such as:

- *Successful experiences with the DARE platform*: focusing on what features contributed to the participants' positive experience using the platform;
- *Ease of use*: discussing what features would make the platform easy to use;
- *Less successful features*: giving the participants an opportunity to reflect on potential drawbacks or features that may be missing from the platform;
- Impact of the platform on *productivity* and *innovation*.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Here are the main findings of the interviews, clustered thematically. An integrated report of the findings has been included in the DARE Deliverable D2.2- M36 report [2].

3.1 Successful experience with DARE

Overall, all the participants found the experience of using DARE successful. Discussing what contributed to the success of the experience, they mentioned the fact that developing targets for use cases were accomplished (N¹=2), and the structure of the platform in itself was deemed to be versatile and functional, because it "*hides some of the complexity of the execution*" (P3). Its components have also been mentioned as contributing to a successful experience with the platform, primarily the workflows that are already set up (N=4), or the fact that DARE sets up the environment with all the libraries that the user may need (P6). P5 also considered that their experience has been successful, while mentioning that the development process is still ongoing. P5 appreciated the facilitation of access to different resources and existing infrastructures. P6 discussed that DARE "*helps to set up a computer environment [...] Since the workflows are already set up, there's no need to set up a cloud cluster for example [...] it reduces the time that a climatologist would need to make the workflow work in a cloud environment.*"

3.1.1 Integration with external and local services

All the participants considered that the platform integrated very well with both external and local services, given the services that were tested so far. Examples of good integration included the European seismic archives which could be downloaded for use (P3). DARE was described as modular and independent thanks to Kubernetes (P4). P5 regarded the DARE platform to be well integrated thanks to the connection to the climate computational resources infrastructure, which is within the workflow, and thus, community-controlled. P5 also mentioned that appropriate software can provide access to the research infrastructure with optimisation, and the DARE API was also deemed beneficial for integration purposes. DARE was described as one of the first platforms to allow the communities to transfer into a cloud, as it is based in BMs (cloud), which should be the future of operations (P6).

3.1.2 Productivity and innovation in communities

All the participants agreed that by using the platform, the productivity of the users would increase. This was motivated by explaining that the platform is aimed at reducing the engineering time by hiding the technical details (N=3), allowing the users to spend more time developing their specific applications and, consequently, on research. More specifically, the platform can be used via an API call, not needing to worry about the workflows or the infrastructure (N=2). P4 discussed that: *“they [users] can just use the platform via an API call,”* not needing to think about the environment and what tools are needed for that. *“The users don’t need to worry about the infrastructure and resources. They just need to develop their application/code and execute it on the platform.”* Time is saved by not fixing the environ or infrastructure to do a job, according to P4.

Most of the participants (N=5) considered that, by reducing the time previously spent on infrastructure complexities, the platform did accelerate innovation in the users’ communities, by enabling them to focus more on research.

3.1.3 Ease of use

The participants generally found the platform easy to use (N=5). We employ caution when presenting this result as all interviewees were in some way involved in its development. As P4 discusses, *“Well, I was developing it, so for me it was easy.”* Nonetheless, the participants were able to identify potential areas for improvement, and suggestions for additional features and training to improve the use of the platform.

3.2 Less successful platform features

The participants discussed these in terms of features that might be missing and could be added, referring to the lack of maturity of the platform, rather than unsuccessful features; “”. Examples included the lack of a user interface, for finding files and logs (P4). Instead they had to use the DARE API for that purpose (P4). The difficulty of installation (P5), the potential assumption that the users should have some cloud computing knowledge to use the platform (P6), as well as computational and programming skills (P3). There was confusion

around the provenance and the API documentation regarding types of data (P2): *“there are some awkward small pieces that are not very detailed in the document.”*

3.3 Training needs for using the platform

All the participants agreed that training would be beneficial for the users and developers. More specifically, an initial training stage was described as essential as the platform has plenty of functionality to offer, and the opportunity and support to explore that in depth should be provided (N=2). Perhaps some training, more specifically aimed at individuals who may not have a background in computer science (N=2), to provide support with the development of workflows and helper functions would be useful. As P2 discussed: *“for some people, especially people not from computer science background related things [...] They are probably having some difficulty understanding what data streaming is and therefore the workflow.”* Providing examples which can be sorted by functions, objectives, etc. was also mentioned (P5). Videos to explain how to register an application, and videos to introduce each aspect of the platform’s functionality (P6) were also provided as examples.

3.3.1 Responsibility for knowledge transfer

All the participants agree that the developers have the initial responsibility for providing support (e.g. to organise webinars). P3 discussed that this responsibility should be shared at institution level, rather than specifically to one person. A collaboration between research engineers and domain-specific engineers was also mentioned (N=2). Lastly, one of the participants (P5) suggested a community forum could be developed over time, similar to Stack Overflow, provided that enough members would actively engage.

With regards to knowledge transfer, some reflections on the speed with which the research engineer would respond to the community requirements were also provided. P3 discussed that it would depend on the community’s interest in the use of the platform. P3 said that research could be sped up research after initial familiarisation delay by *“sharing the tools, methods etc, take what others have developed and improve them.”* Moreover, P3 discussed that *“by exploiting the provenance, you can search for specific experiments with specific data that you used.”* P6 agreed that the response rate would increase for the research engineers from within the communities.

3.4 Automation of research methods and development practices

The participants knew that automation was one of the goals of DARE (to hide some technical details) and they all believe that this was achieved to some extent. More specifically, all resources are shareable between users, by enabling the use and sharing of workflow systems, and large-scale parallelisation without the users’ input. P6 discussed that *“the adoption of workflows enables the applications to scale automatically. The orchestration in DARE (using Kubernetes) allows expansion to more than 1 BM.”*

3.5 Additional automation and functionality

The participants reflected on what additional features could be automated or could further automate processes for the users. Two of the participants discussed that, thanks to the structure of the platform, plenty of features can be added to the platform, depending on community's needs (N=2). The examples provided were graphical interfaces that could particularly be helpful for beginners (P2), the addition of a desktop version with the same libraries, for local deployment (P6), as well as a visual representation of the user's repository (P6) was considered helpful. P5 discussed that, for DARE platform beginners it may be useful *"to provide examples, step-by-step tutorials. [For example] If you could submit your python scripts with additional information on the workflow, it would be good to have an additional tool to generate a workflow ready-made to be run into the DARE platform."* P5 also mentioned that for experts: *"detailed information on how to deploy the platform and how to monitor what's going on/running the platform" may be helpful.*

4 CONCLUSIONS

We would have recruited more participants and conducted more interviews had face-to-face events been possible. The participants supported the view that the platform is usable, and that it would be easy to use (depending on the users' background and skills). The platform supports automation of some common practices, and it allows additional functionality to be added. Training should be provided by developers in the early stages and extended by the communities themselves, to facilitate understanding of the different opportunities enabled by the platform.

We are grateful for the participants' input, and for taking the time to discuss and reflect on different usability aspects of the DARE platform.

REFERENCES

- [1] Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative research in psychology*, 3(2): 77-101.
- [2] DARE. 2020. Deliverable D2.2- M36, Section 5.3.2.

APPENDIX A: Semi-Structured Interview Questions

DARE Interview Questions

1. How do you use data and computers in your daily work?
 - a. How would you define your role?
 - b. Could you describe, please, what skills are expected in this role?
2. What did you (try to) use the DARE platform for?
 - a. Was this experience successful?
 - b. If yes, which of the DARE features helped you be successful? Otherwise, what prevented you from being successful?
3. Did you find it easy to learn how to use the DARE platform (or the application made for you by a DARE research engineer)?
 - a. Follow up: Do you think that users would need to be trained to use the platform?
 - b. If so, do you have any specific ideas/tips regarding that training?
4. (DARE research engineer) Who should be responsible for the knowledge transfer to your user community?
(Application-domain expert) Who should be responsible for the knowledge transfer to the research engineers building tools and services for you?
 - a. How would that impact the speed with which research engineers responded to your community's requirements?
5. To what extent will the DARE platform impact the productivity of application-domain experts/research engineers in their community?
 - a. will it stimulate innovation in your community?
6. (DARE research engineer) How well does the DARE platform integrate with the external / local services you need to use?
(Application-domain expert) How well does the tools and services built with the DARE platform for you integrate with the external / local services you need to use?
7. To what extent does DARE automate, change or enable the research methods / development practices you want?
 - a. What additional automation do you need?
 - b. What additional functionality do you need?
 - c. What would make it easier to use (for beginners or experts)?
8. Do you encounter policies / terms of use / other rules about the use of data?
 - d. How long are they, and how much time do you spend on (finding, reading and understanding) them?
 - e. Do they make your work difficult? E.g. Do you find it difficult to understand and comply with restrictions on the data, resources and code your work depends on? Do you need to go through training before starting?
 - f. Ignoring the difficulty of specifying them, would you like to specify how **your** data (that you produce) or code should be used, either for those data released to the public or not-yet released? (E.g. temporary restriction or long-lasting requirements.)

- g. (Optional) For the software or workflows you run, do you feel some of them will essentially alter the rules applicable to the (output) data?